

Anonymised

Apellidos:

Anonymised

Nombre:

DNI / Pasaporte:

Time: 1 hour 45 minutes

Time and place: Bloque X, 17:00 h

Theory: 60 points

Problems: 60 points

Test. 40 points

Correct answers: + 2 p; **wrong answers:** - 1 p; **non answered questions:** 0 p.

Please, provide your answers to the test in page 5.

1. What is defined as “a set of operational techniques and activities used to verify fulfillment of requirements related to product or service quality”?
 - a. Quality.
 - b. Quality control
 - c. Quality assurance

2. The set of operational techniques and activities focused on providing confidence that quality requirements will be fulfilled is:
 - a. Quality.
 - b. Quality control
 - c. Quality assurance

3. Software quality at the level of project development is:
 - a. A systematic series of actions aiming at managing development time
 - b. A systematic series of actions aiming at managing the development team
 - c. A systematic series of actions aiming at a target

4. Quality views: Which view prevails in the following statements?

	<i>User</i>	<i>Manufacturer</i>	<i>Product</i>	<i>Value</i>	Trascendental
i. Quality is fit for purpose.					
ii. Quality is linked to inherent properties of the product.					
iii. Quality is an ideal we strive to attain.					

5. Which tuple does not belong to the cycle of continuous improvement?
 - a. Do and Analyze
 - b. Plan and Design
 - c. Analyze and Act

6. Which quality tool allows to analyze the existing relationship between two different variables involved in a process?
- Scatter diagram
 - Cause and effect diagram
 - Control chart
7. A histogram:
- Shows the frequency which a given result is repeated.
 - Shows data sorted from highest to lowest
 - Shows the variation of a given variable through time.
8. Quality Deployment function allows to reduce development time without considering customers' wishes.
- True False
9. A process is said to be under statistical control when:
- Causes producing variations are non-assignable.
 - Causes producing variations are assignable.
 - Causes producing variations are controllable
10. An affinity diagram:
- Orders and groups ideas coming from a working group.
 - Represents information obtained when a process or service is studied.
 - Looks for affinities among values of studied variables.
11. Regarding Statistical Process Control (SPC), the Quality Manager of a company states that a statistically controlled process guarantees that it is capable of meeting technical specifications. While the Operations Manager states that the only way for a process to be capable is when its capability index is greater than 1.33, and this is the case for all the company's processes. Which statement do you consider to be more accurate?
- Both statements are false. Human Resources is already searching candidates for both positions.
 - The Quality Manager knows SPC well and she is correct.
 - The Operations Manager has extensive experience with SPC, only his statement is true.
12. Statistical Process Control is:
- A tool that allows to foresee the variations of a process, reduce them and maintain them within reasonable limits.
 - A tool for controlling the production costs of a product.
 - A tool to make sampling plans in a process.

13. A project manager needs a tool that can demonstrate the relationship between events and their resulting effects to illustrate events that cause a negative effect on quality. Which would be the best choice?

- a. Process Flow Diagram.
- b. Ishikawa diagram.
- c. Pareto diagram.

14. Key activities of the measurement process model according to ISO/IEC/IEEE 15939:2017 standard are and in that order:

- a. Preparation for measurement preparation; allocation of resources for measurement process; selection of measurement tools; collection of measurement data.
- b. Establishment of measurement commitments; preparation for measurement; performance of measurement; evaluation of measurement.
- c. Definition of roles and responsibilities; selection of measurement tools; definition of measurement scope; evaluation of measurement results.

15. A measurable concept is:

- a. An abstract relation between attributes of an entity and an information need
- b. An attribute of an entity with a defined measure method, either quantitative or qualitative.
- c. An indicator that combines several measures to determine the quality of an entity.

16. An indicator is:

- a. The value of the degree in which an entity possesses a given quality attribute.
- b. Used to guarantee the management confidence.
- c. A measure that can combine several measures, for which decision criteria are defined with respect to a specific information need.

17. A direct metric is a metric depending on the metric of another attribute, such as the complexity of a program

True

False

18. Some of the benefits of measurement at the organizational level are:

- a. Improve cost control, communication between work groups and identify opportunities for improvement.
- b. Identify opportunities for improvement, improve process workflow and increase return of investment.
- c. Improve cost control and resource management, and communication between workgroups.

19. Some of the benefits of measurement at the project level are:

- a. Improve cost control, resources management, and communication between working groups.
- b. Improve cost control, communication between work groups and identify opportunities for improvement.
- c. Identify opportunities for improvement, improve process workflow, and increase return on investment.

20. Point out an effective metric attribute according to Ejiogu's definition.

- a. Simple and easy to use.
- b. Dependent of programming language.
- c. Consistent and subjective

Test Answers

1.	
2.	
3.	
4. i. 4. ii. 4. iii.	
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Short answer questions. 20 points

1. How is the Risk Priority Number (NPR) calculated in FMEA?
2. Can a process be capable if it is not centered. Justify your answer.
3. List the 7 Quality tools.
4. What is Total Quality?
5. How does the standard ISO9000:2015 define Quality?

Problems. 60 points

Problem 1 (10 puntos)

Errors that are usually dealt with in the claims of the technical service of the company Hardwerizate, S.L. are shown in the following table:

Errors	#
PC does not boot	3
Black screen	100
Unsolicited reboots	40
Overheating	12
Excessive noise	4
Slow or stalled fans	8
USB ports not recognized	10

Represent these data in a Pareto diagram and draw your conclusions.

Problema 2 (20 points)

Business Private Announcement Company (BPA) has taken measures from a critical process and it has obtained the following values expressed in milliseconds:

125,32	125,25	124,95	125,3	124,8	125,05	124,68	125,2	124,75	124,7
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Taking into account that values from this process must be in between $125 \pm 1,2$ ms, please represent the corresponding control chart for variable and analyze the result indicating whether the process is under statistical control or not.

Problema 3 (15 puntos)

With the data from the previous problem, study the process capability and justify whether the process is capable or not.

Problema 4 (15 puntos)

The company Mancuernas Unlimited has arranged an inspection of their products to verify the stability in production. In order to do that, it has verified the conformity of 215 devices a day during 10 days. Gathered data appear in the following table

Días	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Tamaño Muestra	215	215	215	215	215	215	215	215	215	215
Nº No conformes	8	5	7	7	11	9	18	6	8	4

Represent the attribute control chart for non-conforming units and analyze the obtained results.